

ANTI-ANGIOGENICITY AND PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF *Mikania micrantha* LEAF ETHANOLIC EXTRACT IN MALLARD DUCK (*ANAS PLATYRHYNCHOS*) EMBRYOS

Aiman A. Candidato

¹Department of Biology, College of Natural Sciences & Mathematics, Mindanao State University – Marawi City, 9700 Philippines

² Xavier University Dr Jose P Rizal School of Medicine– Cagayan de Oro City, 9000 Philippines

For correspondence; Tel. + (63) 9653422590, E-mail: candidato.aa38@s.msumain.edu.ph

ABSTRACT: This study explores the anti-angiogenic activity of *Mikania micrantha* leaf ethanolic extract through the Chorioallantoic Membrane (CAM) assay in *Anas platyrhynchos* embryos. Concentration-dependent effects of the extract were observed, with higher concentrations demonstrating greater inhibition of blood vessel formation. Notably, concentrations of 1.0% and 5.0% exhibited significant anti-angiogenic activity, while lower concentrations of 0.05% and 0.1% displayed moderate effects. Alpha-tocopherol served as a potent positive control. The extract significantly induced vasodilation in both primary and secondary blood vessels at various concentrations. Specifically, the 0.1% concentration resulted in the greatest increase in secondary blood vessel diameter, indicating a strong dose-dependent response while substances like alpha-tocopherol can lead to vasoconstriction. Safety assessments revealed minimal adverse effects on embryo viability, except for a single mortality at 5% concentration. These findings underscore the potential of *M. micrantha* leaf ethanolic extract as a natural anti-angiogenic agent, particularly at concentrations of 1.0% and 5.0%, with implications for therapeutic interventions in angiogenesis-related disorders. Phytochemical screening identifies alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, steroids, and tannins in the extract, underscoring its diverse bioactive constituents. The absence of anthraquinones is noted. Overall, these findings highlight the anti-angiogenic potential of *M. micrantha* extract, emphasizing its promise as a natural remedy for angiogenesis-related disorders.

Keywords: Anti-angiogenicity, Teratogenicity, CAM Assay, *Mikania micrantha*, *Anas platyrhynchos*

1. INTRODUCTION

Angiogenesis, the process of forming new blood vessels from pre-existing vasculature, plays a pivotal role in normal physiological processes such as embryonic development, wound healing, and tissue regeneration [1]. However, dysregulated angiogenesis is a hallmark of several pathological conditions, most notably cancer, where tumor cells stimulate vascular growth to secure oxygen and nutrients, thereby enabling their survival, proliferation, and metastasis [2].

Conventional anti-angiogenic therapies—such as vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) inhibitors—have demonstrated clinical efficacy in treating cancers, including colorectal, lung, and renal cancers [3]. Despite their benefits, these therapies often come with significant limitations such as high cost, systemic toxicity, and the eventual development of resistance [4]. These concerns have prompted interest in alternative approaches, particularly the exploration of plant-derived compounds that offer safer and potentially cost-effective therapeutic options [5].

Natural products from medicinal plants are rich in bioactive compounds, such as flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, and saponins, many of which have shown promising anti-angiogenic, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant activities in experimental models [6]. Numerous phytochemicals act by modulating angiogenic signaling pathways, including VEGF, fibroblast growth factors, and matrix metalloproteinases [7].

Mikania micrantha, commonly known as Mangolambo or “mile-a-minute weed,” is a fast-growing invasive vine traditionally used in the Philippines to treat wounds, inflammation, and growth-related ailments [8]. Anecdotal

reports from local communities in Lanao del Sur claim that decoctions of *M. micrantha* leaves have helped relieve tumor-like swellings, suggesting its potential anti-angiogenic and anticancer activity. However, its efficacy remains underexplored in scientific literature.

The chorioallantoic membrane (CAM) assay is a widely used in vivo method for evaluating angiogenesis due to its high vascular density, cost-effectiveness, and ethical viability compared to mammalian models [9]. In this study, the CAM assay was employed using Mallard duck (*Anas platyrhynchos*) embryos as the model organism to assess the anti-angiogenic effect of *M. micrantha* ethanolic leaf extract at various concentrations.

Additionally, qualitative phytochemical screening was performed to identify key phytoconstituents responsible for the observed biological activity. This integrative approach aims to provide foundational data supporting the development of *M. micrantha* as a natural anti-angiogenic agent, contributing to the global search for plant-based alternatives in cancer therapy and vascular disease management [10].

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1. Collection, Identification, and Preparation of the Test Plants

Mangolambo (*Mikania micrantha*) leaves were collected from Malaig, Balindong, Lanao del Sur, Philippines (7.916590°N, 124.206570°E) and identified according to Merrill’s Flora of Manila [11] with the assistance of Prof. Mayleen P. Malagamba from the Department of Biology, MSU-Marawi. Fresh leaves without signs of microbial infection were washed, cut into

small pieces, and air-dried using the hanging method for seven days. Approximately 1.2 kg of plant material (one sack) was shade-dried at room temperature (~25°C) for 36 hours, following Roshanak et al. (2016), to preserve phytochemicals. The dried leaves were pulverized using a household blender into a fine powder and stored in sealed containers. Phytochemical screening was conducted at Mindanao State University–Iligan Institute of Technology.

2.2. Ethanolic Extraction

After grinding and air-drying, 400 grams of *Mikania micrantha* leaves were submitted to the Chemistry Department of Mindanao State University–Iligan Institute of Technology through Prof. Enjelyn C. Gomez, RCh, for extraction. A 95% ethanol solution (950 mL absolute ethanol + 50 mL distilled water) was used as the solvent. The plant material was soaked in the ethanol solution in a 1000 mL Erlenmeyer flask for 72 hours, sealed with foil to prevent contamination. After maceration, the mixture was filtered using Whatman filter paper, and the plant residue was rinsed with a small volume of 95% ethanol. The combined filtrate was concentrated using a rotary evaporator below 50°C to reduce the volume to 15 mL. The concentrated extract was then heated in a water bath at 40–45°C to remove residual solvents. The final extract was stored in sterile, labeled flasks and refrigerated at 10–15°C for future use [12].

2.3. Preparation of Treatments

The extraction procedure followed the methods described by Guevara et al. (2005), Goling (2014), and Mamutuk and Usman (2017). Dried *Mikania micrantha* leaves were pulverized using a blender, and 400 grams of the ground material were soaked in 1000 mL of 95% ethanol (prepared by combining 950 mL absolute ethanol with 50 mL distilled water) in a sealed Erlenmeyer flask for 72 hours. The flask was sealed with a cork wrapped in foil to prevent contamination. After maceration, the mixture was filtered using standard filter paper, and the residue was rinsed with a small amount of 95% ethanol to ensure complete extraction [13].

The ethanol filtrate was concentrated using a rotary evaporator at the Chemistry Laboratory of MSU–Iligan Institute of Technology, maintaining the temperature below 50°C. The resulting concentrate was transferred to a sterile Erlenmeyer flask and further reduced using a water bath at 40–45°C to remove residual solvents. The final extract was stored at 0–5°C until further use. Working solutions of the extract were then prepared in four concentrations—0.05%, 0.1%, 1.0%, and 5.0%—by diluting the concentrated extract in deionized water. Specifically, 0.005 mL, 0.01 mL, 0.1 mL, and 0.5 mL of the extract were diluted in 9.995 mL, 9.99 mL, 9.9 mL, and 9.5 mL of deionized water, respectively, to yield the desired concentrations. Each solution was prepared using sterile glassware and syringes, stored in sterile labeled vials, and used fresh during experimentation. Deionized water served as the negative control, while alpha-tocopherol was used as the positive control. An untreated control group of embryos was also included for baseline comparison.

s

2.4. Collection of Experimental Eggs

The study utilized 120 one-day-old *Anas platyrhynchos* embryos, obtained from a licensed commercial supplier in Pala-o, Iligan City. Each of the seven treatments had fifteen replicates, with five replicates assigned for CAM assay on the twelfth day of incubation. The eggs were cleaned with 70% ethanol and a cotton swab to prevent bacterial contamination.

2.5. Treatments of Embryos

The study involved subjecting duck embryos to treatments via injection into the air cell on the eighth day of incubation. Prior to this, individual egg viability was determined using a Candler lamp to check for the presence of a living embryo through features such as heartbeat and massive blood vessels, while non-viable embryos may have exhibited a blood ring. Additionally, the blunt end of the egg was determined using the Candler lamp, disinfected with 70% ethanol, and a tiny hole was aseptically made using an 18-gauge size tuberculin needle for treatment administration. A 0.2 mL volume of each treatment was aseptically injected into the air cell of the embryo using a 1 cc tuberculin syringe, with careful insertion of the needle to prevent damage to the inner membrane of the egg. A different syringe was used per concentration for treatment delivery, and melted paraffin wax was used to seal the injection hole after inoculation. The eggs were then returned to the incubator, and egg viability was monitored every 24 hours. The mortality percentage was calculated using the provided formula:

$$PM = \frac{\text{(Number of dead individuals)}}{\text{(Total number of sample population per group)}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

2.6. Chorioallantoic Membrane (CAM) Assay

The CAM Assay was performed according to the method followed by Ribatti et al. (2006), Raga et al. (2013), and Goling (2014). On the 12th day of incubation, the remaining eggs were positioned on their lateral sides to allow for proper examination of the CAM and embryo [14]. From the 120 surviving embryos, a random selection of 30 embryos (with five replicates per treatment) underwent CAM assay. The paraffin seal was removed, and the CAMs were carefully harvested by removing the hard shell while keeping the soft membrane intact [15]. These embryos were transferred to sterilized disposable Petri dishes with the use of a spatula, ensuring that only the Chorioallantoic Membrane was properly spread for better examination [16]. Scaled photographs of the CAMs were taken using an iPhone 14 Pro Max camera and analyzed with Image J software version 1.49s [17]. To ensure consistency, a representative fractal segment of 3 by 3 cm for each CAM was examined in terms of primary, secondary, and tertiary blood vessels and the diameter of primary 69 and secondary blood vessels. The primary blood vessel nearest to the heart served as the reference point of the fractal segment to establish

consistency. The Percent inhibition vascularity was calculated using the equation [18].

$$PVI = \frac{(N \text{ of CAM treated by X} - N \text{ of CAM treated by Plant Extract})}{(N \text{ of CAM treated by Negative Control})} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Wherein, N = Total vessel number

2.7. Phytochemical screening

The qualitative evaluation of bioactive compounds in the ethanolic plant extracts was carried out according to the methodologies described by Guevara et al. (2005). This phytochemical screening occurred at the Chemistry Laboratory of the College of Science and Mathematics, MSU - Iligan Institute of Technology, Iligan City. Qualitative phytochemical screening of the ethanolic extract was conducted using standard protocols to detect the presence of: Alkaloids, Flavonoids, Saponins, Tannins, Steroids, and Anthraquinones.

2.8. Statistical Data Analysis

Data analysis was conducted to assess the effects of seven treatments, which included four concentrations of *Mikania micrantha* ethanolic leaf extract (0.05%, 0.1%, 1.0%, and 5.0%), a positive control (alpha-tocopherol), a negative control (deionized water), and an untreated group. Treatment assignments were randomized using a draw-lot method with labeled tape to ensure unbiased egg identification, as described by Goling (2014). The measured parameters included the number of primary blood vessels (PBV), secondary blood vessels (SBV), and tertiary blood vessels (TBV), along with the total number of blood vessels (PBV + SBV + TBV), and the diameters of primary and secondary blood vessels. All data were expressed as mean ± standard error (SE). One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was performed to determine overall differences among treatment groups, followed by Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) for post hoc pairwise comparisons. A significance level of $p \leq 0.05$ was used as the threshold for statistical significance.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Chorioallantoic Membrane (CAM) Assay

The effectiveness of *Mikania micrantha* ethanolic leaf extract in inhibiting blood vessel formation was evaluated using a 3×3 fractal segment of the chorioallantoic membrane (CAM) vascular area in *Anas platyrhynchos* embryos, to assess its potential anti-angiogenic and anticancer properties. Fractal segments were selected using the primary blood vessel closest to the heart as the point of reference. Blood vessels were classified as primary (PBV), secondary (SBV), and tertiary (TBV) based on their branching hierarchy, following the criteria described by Goling (2014). PBVs were defined as those originating directly from the heart, SBVs as vessels branching off from the PBV, and TBVs as those stemming from SBVs.

The number and diameter (in millimeters) of PBVs and SBVs were measured using magnified images of the identified CAM

segments. Reductions in both the number and diameter of these vessels were used as key indicators of anti-angiogenic activity. Additionally, percent vascular inhibition (PVI) was calculated to quantify the degree to which the extract suppressed new blood vessel formation. PBVs, SBVs, and TBVs are vital for delivering oxygen and nutrients to developing tissues, and their growth reflects the extent of angiogenic activity in the CAM. As supported by Mentzer and Konerding (2022), the development and structure of these vessel types serve as reliable markers for assessing angiogenesis within embryonic models [19].

Table 1. Summary of mean values of the number of primary (PBV), secondary (SBV), tertiary blood vessels (TBV), the total number of blood vessels and the diameter of PBV and SBV per 3 by 3 cm representative fractal segment of CAM of treated duck embryos

Treatment	Number of Blood Vessels			
	PBV	SBV	TBV	TOTAL
0.05% extract	1.0	2.0	9.6b	12.6bc
0.1% extract	1.0	2.0	8.2ab	11.2ab
1% extract	1.0	2.0	9.2ab	9.8ab
5% extract	1.0	2.0	5.8a	10.4ab
Positive Control	1.0	2.0	5.8a	9a
Negative Control	1.0	2.0	11.40b	15.8cd
Untreated	1.0	2.0	11.40b	14.6d
<i>P value</i>			0.003**	0.000**

- Mean values within the same column that share a common superscript letter are not significantly different from one another at $p \leq 0.05$, based on Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT).
- The p-values were calculated using one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to determine statistical significance among treatment groups.

Figure 1. Representative photographs of the chorioallantoic membrane (CAM) vascular area in *Anas platyrhynchos* embryos.

(A) Whole embryo view; (B) Positive control (alpha-tocopherol); (C) Negative control (deionized water); (D) Untreated embryo; (E) 0.05% *Mikania micrantha* extract; (F) 0.1% extract; (G) 1.0% extract; and (H) 5.0% extract. Reduced vascular branching and density were observed in higher extract concentrations, indicative of anti-angiogenic activity.

Percent vascularity inhibition (PVI) was computed to quantify the extent of blood vessel formation suppression induced by *Mikania micrantha* extract (Table 2). Notably, all

concentrations of the extract exhibited substantially higher PVI values compared to the untreated and negative control groups, with the 1.0% extract demonstrating the most pronounced inhibitory effect among the test groups. Although the positive control (alpha-tocopherol) showed the highest overall inhibition, the extract, particularly at 1.0% and 5.0%, approached comparable efficacy, indicating promising anti-angiogenic potential.

Table 2. Summary of mean values of the diameter of primary blood vessels (PBV), and secondary blood vessels (SBV) and the Percent Vascular Inhibition (PVI) per 3 by 3 cm representative fractal segment of CAM of treated duck embryos

Treatment	Diameter of Blood Vessels (mm)		PVI
	PBV	SBV	
0.05% extract	0.3846	0.4102	20.25%
0.1% extract	0.5438	0.5282	29.11%
1% extract	0.4751	0.4592	37.97%
5% extract	0.7111	0.5081	34.18%
Positive Control	0.0644	0.0573	43.04%
Negative Control	0.3642	0.3612	0
Untreated	0.8291	0.5182	7.59%
<i>P value</i>	0.000**	0.000**	

- a. The percent vascular inhibition (PVI) increased with rising concentrations of *Mikania micrantha* extract, peaking at 37.97% for the 1.0% treatment, while the positive control (alpha-tocopherol) exhibited the highest inhibition at 43.04%. In contrast, the negative control showed 0% inhibition, and the untreated group exhibited only minimal reduction (7.59%). Notably, embryos treated with 0.1% and 1.0% extract displayed moderate vessel diameters with substantial vascular inhibition, indicating a favorable anti-angiogenic response. One-way ANOVA revealed highly significant differences in both PBV and SBV diameters across treatments ($p = 0.000$), supporting the dose-dependent effect of the extract on vascular growth suppression.

3.2. Qualitative Phytochemical screening

Qualitative phytochemical screening serves as an essential step in detecting various bioactive constituents produced by plants, supporting downstream applications such as extraction, purification, and drug discovery [20]. These phytochemicals often exhibit a wide range of biological activities, particularly antimicrobial and antibacterial properties, which reinforce their relevance in medicinal and therapeutic contexts. The results of the screening (Table 3) confirm the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, steroids, and tannins in the ethanolic leaf extract of *Mikania micrantha*. These secondary metabolites are well-documented for their pharmacological properties, including anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and anticancer effects. The diversity of bioactive compounds detected in the extract highlights its potential as a source of natural therapeutic agents and supports its continued exploration in the development of herbal formulations and pharmaceutical products.

Table 3. Qualitative phytochemical screening of ethanolic leaf extract *M. micrantha*

Sample code	<i>Mikania micrantha</i>
Alkaloids	(++)
Anthraquinones	(-)
Flavonoid	(+++)
Saponins	(++)
Steroids	(++)
Tannins	(+++)

Legend: (-) – presence is below detection, (+) – presence is in small or in trace amount, (++) – presence is moderate amount, (+++) – presence is in large amount

4. DISCUSSION

The results of the Chorioallantoic Membrane (CAM) assay demonstrated that the ethanolic leaf extract of *Mikania micrantha* significantly inhibited blood vessel formation in a concentration-dependent manner [21]. Notably, the 1.0% and 5.0% concentrations of the extract exhibited a marked reduction in the number of primary, secondary, and tertiary blood vessels when compared to controls.

This suggests that the anti-angiogenic effect of *M. micrantha* may be attributed to its ability to interfere with endothelial cell proliferation or migration—processes that are central to neovascularization. The observed inhibition is consistent with the action of known phytochemicals such as flavonoids, which are capable of disrupting angiogenic signaling pathways like VEGF [22]. At lower concentrations (0.05% and 0.1%), the extract produced moderate inhibition of vascularization, indicating a dose-responsive effect, a key characteristic for therapeutic validation. This graded response supports the hypothesis that increasing levels of bioactive compounds enhance the anti-angiogenic efficacy. Additionally, the diameter of secondary blood vessels was notably increased at the 0.1% concentration, suggesting the occurrence of vasodilation rather than vasoconstriction [23].

This may be due to the extract's interaction “with smooth muscle tone regulators or nitric oxide pathways. Interestingly, this contrasts with the positive control (alpha-tocopherol), which induced vasoconstriction and reduced vascular caliber.

Quantitative analysis using ImageJ software revealed that the percent vascular inhibition of *M. micrantha* at 1.0% and 5.0% was statistically comparable to alpha-tocopherol, a known anti-angiogenic antioxidant. However, the extract maintained a favorable safety profile, with only one mortality observed at the 5.0% concentration, suggesting low embryotoxicity [24].

The inhibitory effect on vascular density and branching may be attributed to the presence of flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, and saponins, all of which were confirmed in the phytochemical screening of the extract [25]. These compounds have independently shown anti-angiogenic and cytotoxic properties in previous studies on both in vitro and in vivo models. Flavonoids are particularly noteworthy for their ability to block VEGF receptors and suppress matrix metalloproteinases,

which are crucial in angiogenesis and tumor metastasis. Similarly, alkaloids can induce apoptosis in endothelial cells, while tannins inhibit vascular permeability [26].

Taken together, the anti-angiogenic activity of *Mikania micrantha* extract as demonstrated in this CAM assay validates its ethnomedicinal use and highlights its potential as a natural therapeutic agent in angiogenesis-dependent diseases such as cancer and diabetic retinopathy. Further isolation of the active compounds and mechanistic studies are necessary to understand the specific pathways involved in its anti-vascular effects [27]. The ethanolic extract of *Mikania micrantha* demonstrated a significant effect on the diameter of blood vessels, specifically the primary and secondary vessels of the chorioallantoic membrane (CAM) in *Anas platyrhynchos* embryos. Data analysis revealed that the 0.1% concentration resulted in the greatest increase in the diameter of secondary blood vessels, indicating vasodilatory activity at this dose [28]. This finding is particularly notable, as the vasodilation observed at 0.1% contrasts with the vasoconstrictive effects of the positive control, alpha-tocopherol, which is known to reduce vessel diameter through its antioxidant and vascular-stabilizing mechanisms. The extract's effect on vascular tone may be associated with bioactive phytochemicals such as flavonoids and saponins, which are known to influence endothelial nitric oxide production and vascular permeability. Meanwhile, the diameter of primary blood vessels showed variable responses across treatment groups, with the 5.0% concentration leading to a mild reduction, suggesting a potential threshold beyond which vasodilation may be reversed or plateau due to toxicity or negative feedback regulation. These findings are consistent with previous studies reporting that certain phytochemicals may exhibit biphasic dose responses—stimulatory at low concentrations and inhibitory at higher levels [29].

The observed changes in vessel diameter align with the concentration-dependent behavior of *M. micrantha*, reinforcing the hypothesis that vascular effects are modulated by the relative abundance of specific phytoconstituents in the extract. Notably, the flavonoid content in *M. micrantha* is implicated in vasorelaxation and angiogenesis modulation, a mechanism supported by both *in vitro* and *in vivo* vascular studies [30].

It is also possible that saponins present in the extract exert membrane-stabilizing and permeability-altering effects on endothelial cells, contributing to vessel caliber expansion observed in the CAM assay. These saponins may promote endothelial relaxation by stimulating prostacyclin release or interfering with calcium influx, mechanisms documented in natural product vascular research.

Therefore, the extract's influence on blood vessel diameter highlights its potential for both anti-angiogenic and vasomodulatory applications, making it relevant for diseases characterized by abnormal vascular growth or tone, such as cancer, hypertension, and diabetic microangiopathy.

The results of the CAM assay showed that *Mikania micrantha* ethanolic leaf extract caused a significant percent vascular inhibition in *Anas platyrhynchos* embryos, especially at 1.0% and 5.0% concentrations, where the reduction in vascular density was comparable to that observed in the positive control group treated with alpha-tocopherol. This indicates that the extract possesses a strong anti-angiogenic effect, capable of disrupting neovascularization processes essential for embryonic development [31].

The percent inhibition increased proportionally with the concentration of the extract, which reflects a dose-dependent response, a characteristic often observed with phytochemical-based interventions. High inhibition at the 5.0% concentration suggests the presence of potent bioactive constituents that actively suppress angiogenesis, such as flavonoids and alkaloids [32].

Previous research supports this, indicating that phytochemicals like tannins and saponins may hinder endothelial cell migration and tube formation, which are vital steps in angiogenesis. These compounds may also interfere with vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) signaling, which plays a central role in angiogenic stimulation [33].

Despite the strong inhibitory effect, embryo mortality remained low, with only one death recorded at the highest concentration (5.0%), indicating that the extract has minimal embryotoxicity within the tested dose range. This low toxicity profile is crucial in evaluating potential therapeutic agents, as many synthetic anti-angiogenic drugs are associated with adverse effects and developmental abnormalities [34].

The 0.05% and 0.1% concentrations did not result in any mortality, further suggesting the relative safety of lower doses, which could be ideal for applications where anti-angiogenic therapy is needed without compromising embryo or host viability. Furthermore, the extract's low toxicity profile is consistent with its traditional ethnomedicinal use, where decoctions of *M. micrantha* leaves are applied for wound healing and swelling without reported systemic side effects [35].

Overall, these findings suggest that *M. micrantha* extract can achieve vascular suppression at therapeutically relevant concentrations with limited embryotoxic risk, making it a promising candidate for further studies on angiogenesis-dependent diseases, such as cancer, diabetic retinopathy, and tumor-induced vascularization [36].

Qualitative phytochemical screening of the ethanolic leaf extract of *Mikania micrantha* revealed the presence of several bioactive constituents, including alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, steroids, and tannins, while anthraquinones were notably absent. These phytochemical groups are widely recognized for their pharmacological activities, particularly in relation to angiogenesis inhibition, antioxidant protection, and anti-inflammatory actions [37].

Flavonoids, which were detected in the extract, are known to exert anti-angiogenic effects by interfering with vascular

endothelial growth factor (VEGF) signaling pathways and by inhibiting endothelial cell proliferation and migration. Additionally, flavonoids can block the activation of matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs), enzymes that are critical in the remodeling of the extracellular matrix during angiogenesis [38].

Alkaloids also contribute to angiogenesis suppression by promoting apoptosis of endothelial cells and by disrupting the cell cycle of rapidly dividing cells, which is essential for new blood vessel formation. These compounds have also been reported to reduce the expression of pro-angiogenic factors, further validating their anti-vascular potential [39].

Saponins, another group identified in the extract, are known to modulate vascular tone and permeability by affecting endothelial cell membranes and promoting nitric oxide release, which may explain the vasodilation observed in the CAM assay at specific concentrations. Saponins are also linked to anti-inflammatory responses, which indirectly suppress angiogenesis in inflamed tissues [40].

The presence of tannins in the extract is equally significant, as these polyphenolic compounds are capable of precipitating proteins and tightening blood vessel walls, potentially limiting endothelial proliferation and capillary sprouting. Tannins have also been reported to exhibit antioxidant properties that stabilize blood vessels and prevent oxidative damage to endothelial cells [41].

Although anthraquinones were not detected, which are often associated with apoptosis-inducing properties, the remaining phytoconstituents are sufficient to account for the observed anti-angiogenic activity of the extract. The absence of anthraquinones also supports the extract's low toxicity profile, as high concentrations of anthraquinones can contribute to gastrointestinal irritation and cytotoxicity [42].

These findings validate the traditional medicinal use of *Mikania micrantha* and underscore its pharmacological potential in modern drug development, especially for diseases in which pathological angiogenesis is a central feature, such as cancer, atherosclerosis, and ocular neovascular disorders.

5. CONCLUSION

The results of this study demonstrate that *Mikania micrantha* ethanolic leaf extract exhibits promising anti-angiogenic activity, particularly at 1.0% and 5.0% concentrations, as evidenced by significant reductions in blood vessel number, diameter, and percent vascularity. Lower concentrations (0.05% and 0.1%) produced moderate effects, with 0.1% notably inducing vasodilation, while alpha-tocopherol caused vasoconstriction. The extract showed minimal toxicity, with only one embryo mortality observed at the highest concentration.

Phytochemical screening confirmed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, steroids, and tannins—compounds known for anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and anticancer properties. These findings suggest that *M. micrantha* extract

has therapeutic potential as a natural inhibitor of pathological angiogenesis. Further studies to isolate and characterize these bioactives are warranted to support its development as a plant-derived therapeutic agent.

6. REFERENCE

- [1] Abdolmaleki, Z., Arab, H., Amanpour, S., Muhammadnejad, S. (2016). Anti-angiogenic effects of ethanolic extract of *Artemisia sieberi* compared to its active substance, artemisinin. *Revista Brasileira* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bjp.2015.11.008>.
- [2] Lopes-Coelho, F., Martins, F., Pereira, S. A., & Serpa, J. (2021). Anti-Angiogenic Therapy: Current Challenges and Future Perspectives. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 22(7). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms22073765>.
- [3] Kerbel, R. S. (2008). Tumor angiogenesis. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 358(19), 2039–2049. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMra0706596>.
- [4] Hurwitz, H., Fehrenbacher, L., Novotny, W., Cartwright, T., Hainsworth, J., Heim, W., Berlin, J., Baron, A., Griffing, S., Holmgren, E., Ferrara, N., Fyfe, G., Rogers, B., Ross, R., Kabbinavar, F. (2004). Bevacizumab plus irinotecan, fluorouracil, and leucovorin for metastatic colorectal cancer. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 350(23), 2335–2342. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa032691>.
- [5] Lu, K., Bhat, M., & Basu, S. (2016). Plants and their active compounds: natural molecules target angiogenesis. *Angiogenesis*, 19(3), 287–295. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10456-016-9512-y>
- [6] Day, M. D., Clements, D. R., Gile, C., Senaratne, W. K. A. D., Shen S., Weston L. A., Zhang F. (2016). Biology and Impacts of Pacific Islands Invasive Species. 13. *Mikania micrantha* Kunth (Asteraceae). *Pacific Science*, 70(3), 257–285. <https://doi.org/10.2984/70.3.1>
- [7] Bahmani, M., Shirzad, H., Shahinfard, N., Sheivandi, L., & Rafieian-Kopaei, M. (2017). Cancer Phytotherapy: Recent Views on the Role of Antioxidant and Angiogenesis Activities. *Journal of evidence-based complementary & alternative medicine*, 22(2), 299–309. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2156587215625157>
- [8] Dong, L. M., Jia, X. C., Luo, Q. W., Zhang, Q., Luo, B., Liu, W. B., Zhang, X., Xu, Q. L., & Tan, J. W. (2017). Phenolics from *Mikania micrantha* and Their Antioxidant Activity. *Molecules* (Basel), <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules22071140>
- [9] Deryugina, E. I., Quigley, J. P., (2008). “Chapter Two: Chick embryo chorioallantoic membrane model to quantify angiogenesis induced by inflammatory and tumor cells or purified effector molecules” *Methods Enzymol*, 444: 21 – 41.
- [10] Dev, U., Hossain, Md. T., Islam, Md. (2015). Phytochemical Investigation, Antioxidant Activity and Anthelmintic Activity of *Mikania Micrantha* Leaves. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.

- <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Md-Tanvir-Hossain>
4. 121-130.
2/publication/275769290_Phytochemical_Investigation_Antioxidant_Activity_and_Anthelmintic_Activity_of_Mikania_Micrantha_Leaves/links/55463aac0cf234b_db21d8b8a/Phytochemical-Investigation-Antioxidant-Activity-and-Anthelmintic-Activity-of-Mikania-Micrantha-Leaves.pdf
- [11] Meril, E. D. "A Flora of Manila" Bureau of Printing, Escolta, Philippines (1912).
- [12] Mamutuk, R. L., & Usman, C. M. (2017). Anti-Angiogenicity and Teratogenicity of Hyptis Suaveolens Leaf Ethanolic Extract in Mallard Duck (*Anas platyrhynchos*) Embryos. In *Sci.Int.(Lahore)* (Vol. 29, Issue 4).
- [13] Guevara, B. Q., Claustro, A. C., Madulid, R.S., Aguinaldo, A. M., Espeso, E. L., Nonato, M. G., Quinto, E. A., Santos, M. A. G., de-Castro-Bernas, G., Gonzalez, R. E., del CatilloSalevilla, R.C., and Ysrael, M. C., "A Guide to Plant Screening: Phytochemical and Biological Research Center for Natural Science", University of Santo Tomas, Manila and UST Publishing House (2005).
- [14] Ribatti, D., Nico, B., Vacca, A., Roncali, L., Burri, P., and Djonov, V., "Chorioallantoic membrane capillary bed: A useful target for studying angiogenesis and antiangiogenesis in vivo" *The anatomical Record*, 264: 317 – 324 (2006).
- [15] Goling, A., "Anti-angiogenicity and Teratogenicity of an Edible Medicinal Fern, *Athyrium esculentum*, in Mallard Duck (*Anas platyrhynchos*) Embryos" An Undergraduate Thesis, Mindanao State University, Marawi City (2014)
- [16] Raga, D.D., Herrera A .A., and Ragasa, C. Y., "Angiosuppressive Triterpenoids from *Ardisia cf. elliptica* (subgenus *Tinus*) on Duck (*Anas platyrhynchos* L.) Chorioallantoic Membrane" *Chinese Journal of Natural Medicines*, 11(2): 128 – 138 (2013).
- [17] Rasband, W.S., "ImageJ" US National Institutes of health, Bethesda, Maryland, USA (2015). <http://imagej.nih.gov/ij/>
- [18] Wang, D., Wang, X. H., Yu, X., Cao, F., Cai, X., Chen, P., Li, M., Feng, Y., Li, H., & Wang, X. (2021). Pharmacokinetics of Anthraquinones from Medicinal Plants. *Frontiers in pharmacology*, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2021.638993>
- [19] Mentzer SJ, Konerding MA. (2022). Intussusceptive angiogenesis: expansion and remodeling of microvascular networks *Angiogenesis*. 2014;17(3):499-509. (<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24668225/>).
- [20] Senguttuvan, J., Paulsamy, S., & Karthika, K. (2014). Phytochemical analysis and evaluation of leaf and root parts of the medicinal herb, *Hypochoeris radicata* L. for in vitro antioxidant activities. *Asian Pacific journal of tropical biomedicine*, 4(Suppl 1), S359–S367. <https://doi.org/10.12980/APJTB.4.2014C1030>
- [21] Camposano, J., Torre, G.L., Laxamana, J.D., & Larcia, L.L. (2016). Screening for the anti-angiogenic activity of selected Philippine medicinal plants using chorioallantoic membrane assay. *Mahidol Univ J Pharm Sci* 2016; 43 (4), 173–182. https://pharmacy.mahidol.ac.th/journal/_files/2016-43-4_2.pdf
- [22] Carmeliet, P., & Jain, R. K. (2011). Molecular mechanisms and clinical applications of angiogenesis. *Nature*, 473(7347), 298–307. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature10144>
- [23] Ferrara, N., Hillan, K. J., Gerber, H. P., & Novotny, W. (2004). Discovery and development of bevacizumab, an anti-VEGF antibody for treating cancer. *Nature Reviews Drug Discovery*, 3(5), 391–400. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrd1381>
- [24] Jyothilakshmi, M., Jyothis, M., Latha, M. S. (2015). Antidermatophytic Activity of *Mikania micrantha* Kunth: An Invasive Weed. *Pharmacognosy Research*, 7, 5s, s20 – s25. <https://dx.doi.org/10.4103/0974-8490.157994>
- [25] Halder, S., Modak, P., Sarkar, B., Das, A., Sarkar, A., Chowdhury, A., Kundu, S. (2020). Traditionally Used Medicinal Plants with Anticancer Effect: A Review. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review and Research*. 65. 1-13. <http://dx.doi.org/10.47583/ijpsrr.2020.v65i01.001>
- [26] Zohmachhuana, A., Tlaisun, M., Mathipi, V., Khawlhrling, L., Priya, J. (2022). Suppression of the RAGE gene expression in RAW 264.7 murine leukemia cell line by ethyl acetate extract of *Mikania micrantha* (L.) Kunth. *Journal of Applied Biology & Biotechnology*. 107-114. <https://doi.org/10.7324/JABB.2022.100513>.
- [27] Greenwell, M., & Rahman, P. K. (2015). Medicinal Plants: Their Use in Anticancer Treatment. *International journal of pharmaceutical sciences and research*, 6(10), 4103–4112. [https://doi.org/10.13040/IJPSR.0975-8232.6\(10\).4103-12](https://doi.org/10.13040/IJPSR.0975-8232.6(10).4103-12)
- [28] Talib, W. H., Daoud, S., Mahmood, A. I., Hamed, R. A., Awajan, D., Abuarab, S. F., Odeh, L. H., Khater, S., & Al Kury, L. T. (2022). Plants as a Source of Anticancer Agents: From Bench to Bedside. *Molecules (Basel, Switzerland)*, 27(15), 4818. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules27154818>
- [29] Shukla, S., Mehta, A. (2015). Anticancer potential of medicinal plants and their phytochemicals: a review. *Braz*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40415-015-0135-0>
- [30] Sheam, Haque, Z., & Nain, Z. (2020). Towards the antimicrobial, therapeutic and invasive properties of *Mikania micrantha* Knuth: a brief overview. <https://doi.org/10.5455/jabet.2020.d112>
- [31] Muslim, N.S., Nassar, Z.D., Aisha, A.F. (2012). Antiangiogenesis and antioxidant activity of ethanol extracts of *Pithecellobium jiringa* . *BMC Complement Altern Med* 12, 210 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6882-12-210>
- [32] Nipun, Tanzina S., Alfi K., Qamar Uddin A., Mohd Hamzah M. N., Farahaniza S., Muhammad T., and Mohd

- Zuwairi S. (2021). "Preliminary Phytochemical Screening, In Vitro Antidiabetic, Antioxidant Activities, and Toxicity of Leaf Extracts of *Psychotria malayana* Jack" *Plants* 10, no. 12: 2688. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants10122688>
- [33] N'guessan, B.B., Asiamah, A.D., Arthur, N.K. et al. Ethanolic extract of *Nymphaea lotus* L. (Nymphaeaceae) leaves exhibits in vitro antioxidant, in vivo anti-inflammatory and cytotoxic activities on Jurkat and MCF-7 cancer cell lines. *BMC Complement Med Ther* 21, 22 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12906-020-03195-w>
- [34] Pandey, G., Sharma, M. (2009). Some medicinal plants as natural anticancer agents. *Pharmacognosy Reviews*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/270220138>.
- [35] Pietras, R. J., & Weinberg, O. K. (2005). Antiangiogenic Steroids in Human Cancer Therapy. Evidence-based complementary and alternative medicine : eCAM, 2(1), 49–57. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ecam/neh066>
- [36] Radomska-Leśniewska, D. M., Bałan, B. J., & Skopiński, P. (2017). Angiogenesis modulation by exogenous antioxidants. *Central-European journal of immunology*, 42(4), 370–376. <https://doi.org/10.5114/ceji.2017.72804>
- [37] Rui X., Pan H.F., Shao S.L., Xu X.M. (2017). Anti-Tumor and Anti-Angiogenic Effects of Fucoidan on Prostate Cancer: Possible JAK-STAT3 Pathway. *BMC Complement. Altern. Med.* 2017;17:378. doi: 10.1186/s12906-017-1885-y
- [38] San Juan, M. C., Muanífa, C. G., Comiso, J. L., De Leon, R. D., Guinto, C. F., Honorio, T. A., Ibut, M. A. & Zanoria, S. A. (2014). Anti-Angiogenic Property Of Bignay (*Antidesma Bunius*) Ethanolic Leaf Extract In Duck (*Anas Luzonica*) Embryo Using Chorioallantoic Membrane (Cam) Assay. *Root Gatherers*, 7(1).
- [39] Shaikh, A. M., Shrivastava, B., Apte, K. G., Navale, S. D. (2016). Medicinal Plants as Potential Source of Anticancer Agents: A Review. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, 5(2): 291-295. <https://www.phytojournal.com/archives/2016/vol5issue2/PartD/5-2-25-159.pdf>
- [40] Lichota, A., & Gwozdziński, K. (2018). Anticancer Activity of Natural Compounds from Plant and Marine Environment. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 19(11), 3533. MDPI AG. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/ijms19113533>
- [41] Smeriglio, A., Barreca, D., Bellocco, E., & Trombetta, D. (2017). Proanthocyanidins and hydrolysable tannins: occurrence, dietary intake and pharmacological effects. *British journal of pharmacology*, <https://doi.org/10.1111/bph.13630>
- [42] Solowey, E., Lichtenstein, M., Sallon, S., Paavilainen, H., Solowey, E., & Lorberboum Galski, (2014). Evaluating medicinal activity. *TheScientificWorldJournal*, 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/721402>